

European Values Study

WageIndicator.org

Processing & analysis

SurveyCodings

Socio-economic and more general social science variables are widely used in research. However, these variables cannot be measured with scales but require detailed and elaborate categorical classification systems. Some variables also come along with a larger number of answer categories challenging their measurement. The developed tools reduce office coding, less harmonization logistics and save costs by linking survey questionnaires to databases to allow the coding of survey variables during the interview. Database lookups can either replace open questions that need to be post-coded or long-list questions. Tools for several variables are developed and extended within SSHOC and available at surveycodings.org.

SurveyCodings

Tool

What is SurveyCodings

Surveycodings is a free service for social science projects, data archives and researchers measuring individual and socio-economic variables. It provides a multilingual repository containing questionnaires, data collection tools, and coding frames based on standard statistical classifications for a large number of countries. SurveyCodings covers the following variables: occupation, industry, levels and fields of education, region, food groups, religions, cost of living, and marital status, all coded according to ruling standards.

The coding sets use standard classifications to organize and code information and to enable input harmonization at data collection stage resulting in more consistent data, especially for cross-national data collection. Our services aim at developing solutions for fast high quality cost-effective cross-national harmonized coding for key variables. The coding tools use a dictionary containing tens of thousands of entries about job titles, industry names, religions, and fields of education. In addition, we provide country-specific, structured lists of educational qualifications, religious denominations and occupations. The code frames are provided using international standardized classifications, so that they can be used in cross national surveys such as SHARE, ESS, EVS, GGP, ISSP.

These coding sets can be used for respondent's self-selection or interviewer's selection during computer-assisted survey. It is also possible to use the coding sets as a resource for post-coding of the answers, e.g. of open-ended questions in order to achieve harmonized comparable data. To have a closer look at the different coding sets, the webpage provides a database live search separately for each variable and a demo questionnaire including all variables.

Key features

- ➔ Provides measurement instruments for individual and socio-economic variables that can be implemented in surveys;
- ➔ Coding sets can also be used for post-coding;
- ➔ Users can download the coding sets, questionnaires, source codes and review background information;
- ➔ The sets for food items or religions will help respondents in surveys to easier identify how they spend their budget or identify their actual religion;
- ➔ Some coding sets can be linked in view of specific research questions, e.g. industries to occupations, occupations to education;
- ➔ Classifications can be applied to the complete set in one go;
- ➔ Ready to use detailed and comparable data for survey agencies;
- ➔ Coding sets can be used for deeply scrutinizing a single-country case or for comparing at a higher level multiple countries.

Benefits

- ➔ Standardized instruments lead to higher comparability of the data across surveys using these instruments. So far, surveys use standard classifications derived from quite different measurement instruments, which lead to inconsistent and not comparable data; Ex-ante structured modules in different modes and formats;
- ➔ Website's functionality can be stored in an app that can be used on a mobile device; The infrastructure offers the opportunity of keeping the coding sets updated if deemed necessary; Data can automatically be easier compared, and no office coding is needed to harmonize the data; There is no longer a need to ask respondents to find their occupations or religion in a limited set of aggregated categories;
- ➔ Zoomed insight into national key sectors.

Contributors

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Access SurveyCodings

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Tool

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